

**GLOBAL PRICE OF ALUMINUM AND SOLAR ACTIVITY (1990–
2024): R2=0.93
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Abstract

This report uses a methodological approach developed by W. S. Jevons and A. L. Chizhevsky. During the study period, solar cycle years were numbered according to the order established in solar astrophysics, grouped, and compared with the average arithmetic values of aluminum prices per ton. The resulting model has a determination coefficient of 0.93, with a p-value of 0.0087. This model yields a projected aluminum price of \$2,091.76 per ton in 2026 and \$2,368.64 per ton in 2027.

Keywords

Aluminum price, solar activity cycles, Wolf numbers, economic cycles

In his article "Solar-Commercial Cycles" W. S. Jevons plotted solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and Delhi corn price cycles one above the other for the period 1760–1810 [1, P.227], that is, he compared solar and economic activity.

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph "The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun" in Chapter 4 "The Sun and Epidemics" in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that depicts the average solar activity cycle over a hundred years (the Wolf number cycle) and the average cases of cholera in Russia for the years of the solar cycle for the period 1823–1923 [2, p. 201]. That is, he applied the method of superimposing eras.

In this study, a single diagram compares the numbers of years in the average solar cycle and the arithmetic mean values of the price of aluminum for 1990–2025.

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity (SA), were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [3]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The ordinal numbers of years in column 3 of Table 1 are determined as follows. The first year in a SA cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, that is, the increase in the Wolf number, which is presented in column 2. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the SA minimum. Years of Wolf number minimums in Table 1 are highlighted in blue. Years of maximums are highlighted in red.

The Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis website provides statistical data on annual world aluminum prices for the period 1990–2025 [4]. These are presented in column 4 of Table 1.

Таблица 1. Среднегодовые числа Вольфа, порядковые номера лет в циклах СА и средние годовые мировые цены на алюминий, 1990–2025

1. The years	2. Wolf numbers	3. The serial number of the year in the cycle of SA	4. Global price of Aluminum, dollars per ton,
1990	191.8	4	1639.50
1991	203.3	5	1304.02
1992	133	6	1256.27
1993	76.1	7	1139.93
1994	44.9	8	1475.63
1995	25.1	9	1805.02
1996	11.6	10	1506.79
1997	28.9	1	1599.29
1998	88.3	2	1357.57
1999	136.3	3	1359.99
2000	173.9	4	1551.50
2001	170.4	5	1446.75
2002	163.6	6	1351.06
2003	99.3	7	1432.82
2004	65.3	8	1718.50
2005	45.8	9	1900.51
2006	24.7	10	2573.06
2007	12.6	11	2639.86
2008	4.2	12	2577.92
2009	4.8	1	1668.49
2010	24.9	2	2172.99

2011	80.8	3	2400.64
2012	84.5	4	2022.80
2013	94	5	1846.68
2014	113.3	6	1867.42
2015	69.8	7	1664.68
2016	39.8	8	1604.18
2017	21.7	9	1967.65
2018	7	10	2108.47
2019	3.6	11	1794.49
2020	8.8	1	1704.10
2021	29.6	2	2472.95
2022	83.2	3	2706.99
2023	125.5	4	2256.09
2024	154.6	5	2420.95
2025	123.2	6	2630.62
2026		7	

The statistical data in Table 1 were then grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. Column 2 of Table 2 shows the number of years with a given ordinal number for the period 1990–2025.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles

1. The serial number of the year in the cycle of SA	2. The number of such years for the period 1990–2025	Arithmetic mean:		5. Relative to the previous year's price.
		3. Wolf number	4. Global price of Aluminum, dollars per ton	
1	3	14.17	1657.29	0.64
2	3	47.60	2001.17	1.21
3	3	100.10	2155.87	1.08
4	4	143.93	1867.47	0.87
5	4	155.58	1754.60	0.94
6	4	133.28	1776.34	1.01
7	3	81.73	1412.48	0.80
8	3	50.00	1599.44	1.13
9	3	30.87	1891.06	1.18
10	3	14.43	2062.78	1.09
11	2	8.10	2217.17	1.07
12	1	4.20	2577.92	1.16
Итого:	36			

Based on columns 1 and 4 of Table 2, a diagram is constructed in Figure 1. The coefficient of determination is 0.93, and the p-value is 0.0087. The trend equation is statistically significant at $p < 0.01$. With a reliability of over 99%, it can be concluded that the identified cyclical relationship between the global aluminum price and the SA cycle year numbers is not a coincidence.

Fig. 1. World prices for aluminum and serial numbers of years of the SA cycles for 1990–2025, 36 years of observations, method of superposing eras

The year 2026's index number in the current 25th SA cycle is 7 (see Table 1). The ratio of the price in year 7 to that in year 6 is 0.80. Therefore, the projected price of aluminum in 2026 is $0.8 * 2630.62 = \$2091.76$ per ton.

Figure 1 shows that point 6, which includes 2025, deviates from the general trend line. This demonstrates the influence of other factors (wars, sanctions, and others) that can lead to inaccuracies in a forecast based solely on SA.

The year 2027's index number in the current 25th SA cycle is 8 (see Table 1). The ratio of the price in year 8 to that in year 7 is 1.13. Therefore, the projected price of aluminum in 2027 is $1.13 * 2091.76 = \$2368.64$ per ton.

Based on rows 1–5 (years of SA growth) and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, the following diagram is constructed in Figure 2. For the presented quadratic model (second-degree polynomial), the achieved significance level is $p = 0.0018$, which indicates high statistical significance ($p < 0.01$).

Fig. 2. Years of SA growth and world prices for aluminum, 17 years of observations for 1990–2025, superposition method

Based on rows 5–12 (years of SA decline) and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, the following diagram is constructed in Figure 3. For this 3rd-degree (cubic) model, the achieved significance level is $p=0.0056$, which indicates high statistical significance ($p < 0.01$).

The approximating functions in the diagrams in Figures 2 and 3 allow us to obtain global aluminum price forecasts based on the predicted Wolf number. The predicted Wolf number can be determined based on the current NASA forecast, which is presented in Figure 4.

Fig. 3. Years of decline in the CA (Wolf numbers) and world prices for aluminum, 19 years of observations for 1990–2025

Fig. 4. Forecast of the development of the current 25th SA cycle

I previously proposed calling the science that studies the connections between solar and economic activity helioeconomics.

Reference

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